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Gender Difference in University Students' Engineering Creative in Taiwan

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INTRODUCTION

Creativity is a fundamental element of engineering [5]. Creativity is concerned with the generation of effective, novel solutions to problems, while engineering, and engineering education have a similar goal, focused on technological solutions [9]. In recent years, creativity has become one of the most important issues in engineering education in Taiwan. Many trans-disciplinary projects in Taiwan have focused on the subject and hundreds of web pages display information on how to be more creative and achieve innovation in engineering. Studying university students' creativity is very critical for acquiring in-depth understanding of engineering education for educators and researchers who take great interest in education- or engineering-related fields.

It has been emphasized that more females should be able to contribute to society in the engineering field [11]. Abraham [1] proposed that gender is an important affecting factor to creativity. As Kang and Yune [11] indicated that studying gender differences of creativity in engineering is important and practical in providing educational materials or teaching interventions for both male and female university students in the engineering field. Therefore, the main purpose of this study was to analyze engineering university students' creativity by examining a sample of students in Taiwan. In addition, this study is to investigate the relationship between students' gender and engineering creativity.

PERSPECTIVES

Since Guilford [10] proposed the definitions of creativity in 1950, the issue of creativity research had been scrutinized by researchers. Then Torrance [20] applied Guilford's creativity theory to draw a framework for creative thinking processes that consists of four aspects: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. Fluency refers to the production of a great number of ideas or alternate solutions to a problem. Flexibility refers to the production of ideas that show a variety of possibilities or realms of thought. Originality involves the production of ideas that are unique or unusual. Elaboration is the process of enhancing ideas by providing more detail. Recently, Charyton [4] contended that engineers not only need to address esthetics like artists, but also to solve problems, prevent potential problems, and address utility within the constraints and parameters that have been designated. These aspects of creativity have been described as "functional creativity," [7] which means that products designed by engineers typically serve a functional and useful purpose. Building on this, problem finding offers another avenue for increasing creative production [13]. Problem solving skills are often found in and commonly associated with art, yet are also necessary in science and engineering. However, these attributes have not been specifically measured traditionally nor in engineering creativity. Such attributes need to be assessed and further developed by appropriate educational intervention activities [7]. Mainly adopting the definition of

creativity by Torrance [20] and covering the dimension proposed by Cropley and Cropley [7], this study led to the development of a framework of an instrument for measuring students' engineering creativity, which contained five dimensions: fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration, and usefulness.

Abraham [1] proposed that gender is an important factor. Since researchers began to focus on gender differences in creativity, no simple conclusion has been drawn from the empirical evidence on this issue. For example, some studies considered that there were no gender differences in creativity [12] [16] [19], while some studies reported that females tended to score higher than their male counterparts in creativity [2] [17] [14]. Some other studies indicated some opposite results with males scoring higher than females [6] [15]. The conflicting outcomes could be results of tests being conducted in different cultural contexts. On the other hand, most studies of creativity tended to focus on general creativity, not creativity narrowing to that revolving around engineering, especially with gender factor completely overlooked. Therefore, this study was intended to explore the gender differences in engineering creativity in Taiwan.

METHODS

3.1 Measures methods. The instrument used in this study was "The Engineering Creativity Scale (ECS), developed by authors to measure university students' engineering creativity. The ECS consisted of two sub-tests: "Design of generating sound" and "Design a car" which were derived and revised from Charyton's [4] and Yeh's [21] studies with minor changes according to the Mandarin usage and local culture. The "Design of generating sound" was designated to ask participants to draw two designs (Design 1 and Design 2) based on two 3-dimension images. The participants were asked to describe each of their two designs by answering the following questions: "What is your design?", "What are the materials of your designs", "What are the problems solved with your designs", and "Who will be users of your designs". The second subtest, "Design a car", required participants to draw a car with their imagination and design. Subsequently, the participants were asked to describe the features and specifics of the car they designed and used pens to draw their designed products on the ECS. The amount of test time was 30 minutes: 10 minutes for Design of generating sound, and 20 minutes for Design a car.

The coefficients of internal consistency reliability of the ECS were between .12-.90, $p < .001$. The coefficients of test/re-test reliability were between .32-.50, $p < .05$. The coefficients of inter-rater reliability were between .47-.97, $p < .001$. The coefficients of parallel-forms reliability were between .30-.50, $p < .01$.

Regarding the validity of the ECS, six university professors in engineering or psychology were asked to determine the content validity of the ECS by rigorously and

thoroughly reviewing the item content of the ECS. And the ECS was modified based on these experts' suggestions and comments. In addition, the coefficients of criterion-related validity were applied and were ranged from .25-.55, $p < .05$.

3.1 Data resource. This ECS was given in a group administration to assess university students' creativity in engineering. A sample of 104 university students who studied in the engineering field from 3 (2 public and 1 private) universities in Taiwan was invited to participate in this research voluntarily, from April to November 2017. As shown in Table 1, the sample included 59(55.7%) males and 47(44.3%) females, and consisted of 12(11.3%) freshman, 26(24.5%) sophomore, 51(48.1%) junior and 17 (16.0%) senior students.

Table 1 The distributions of samples in this study

	Male		Female		TOTAL	
	<i>N</i>	%	<i>N</i>	%	<i>N</i>	%
School type						
Public	40	37.7	30	28.3	70	66.0
Private	19	17.9	17	16.0	36	34.0
TOTAL	59	55.7	47	44.3	106	100
Grade						
Freshman	5	4.7	7	6.6	12	11.3
Sophomore	16	15.1	10	9.4	26	24.5
Junior	29	27.4	22	20.8	51	48.1
Senior	9	8.5	8	7.5	17	16.1
TOTAL	59	55.7	47	44.3	106	100

3.3 Analytic strategy. The following procedural steps were used to score each participant's answer. The Design of generating sound consisted of four dimensions: fluency, flexibility, originality, and usefulness. Fluency was computed by the number of ideas on the sketch, description, materials, problems solved, and potential users. Flexibility was calculated by the number of different categories, types, or classifications of responses. Originality was scored by a 11-point scale (0 = dull, 1 = commonplace, 2 = somewhat interesting, 3 = interesting, 4 = very interesting, 5 = insightful, 6 = unique and different, 7 = exceptional, 8 = innovative, 9 = valuable and beneficial to the field, and 10 = genius). Usefulness was scored with a 5-point scale (0 = not useful, 1 = somewhat useful, 2 = moderately useful, 3 = very useful, and 4 = indispensable). At first, Design 1 and Design 2 were scored separately, and then scores of Design 1 and Design 2 were summed up for each dimension, respectively.

“Design a car” included four dimensions: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. The fluency score was given simply by counting all the valid responses given by the participants. The flexibility score was given by counting the numbers of categories of students’ answers on the car features. The originality score was developed from a tabulation of the frequency of all the responses obtained. Frequencies and percentages of each response were computed. Among all answers, 2 points were given to a special answer for the originality score when the probability of this answer was smaller than 5%. One point was given to an answer of which the probability was between 5% and 10%. The elaboration was obtained by counting the numbers of car specifics given by participants. The total score of “Design of generating sound” for each participant was computed by summing up his/ her T scores of fluency, flexibility, originality, and usefulness. The total score of “Design a car” was computed by adding up the T scores of fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. The combined scores of engineering creativity for each participant were computed by averaging scores of these two subtests’ scores.

Moreover, in order to explore the relationship between students’ gender and creativity, the independent *t* test was employed to test the significant difference between male and female in each of five dimensions and the total score of the ECS.

RESULTS

The results of this study, shown in Table 2, have some interesting findings. (1) The range of the means of five dimensions from males is 50.27 to 55.19 (T Score), from high to low: Usefulness, Fluency, Flexibility, Originality, and Elaboration, and the total score is 52.04. (2) The range of the means of five dimensions from females is 48.03 – 50.67 (T Score), from high to low: Usefulness, Flexibility, Fluency, Elaboration, and Originality, and the total score is 48.94. (3) Male students score significantly higher than female students in Fluency ($t(104) = 2.75, p < .01$), Originality ($t(104) = 2.27, p < .05$), Usefulness ($t(104) = 2.26, p < .05$) and the total score ($t(104) = 2.69, p < .01$). Nevertheless, there is no significant gender difference in scores of Flexibility and Elaboration.

Table 2 The summary of university students’ gender and engineering creativity

Dimension	Male (<i>n</i> =59)		Female (<i>n</i> =47)		<i>t</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	
Fluency	52.32	6.48	48.82	6.53	2.75**
Flexibility	51.98	6.25	49.52	7.84	1.80
Originality	51.05	7.48	48.03	5.86	2.27*
Elaboration	50.27	9.48	48.06	8.55	1.25
Usefulness	55.19	12.13	50.67	8.38	2.26*

Total	52.04	5.85	48.94	5.99	2.69**
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* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

DISCUSSION

Results above present some interesting and noteworthy findings. Firstly, both male and female participants score highest in Usefulness among the five dimensions of engineering creativity. The participants' responses to the test corresponded positively to Charyton's [4] point that problem solving or the utility of product should be designated or described in the product designing process.

Secondly, male participants score significantly higher than female participants in Fluency, Originality, Usefulness and the total score. The results of this study differ from previous studies, such as those conducted by Bender, Nibbelink, Towner-Thyrum, & Vredenburg [2], in which females scored significantly higher than males. However, the results of this study partially support Kang & Yune's [11] finding that Korean female engineering students had lower scores on both the integrated creativity and engineering creativity tests than male students. Does this imply that Asian's culture and learning environment are more supportive for male than for female students in their creativity development in the engineering field? It is cortical for the faculty can promote female students to practice creativity thinking skills by giving more opportunities to promote females' engineering creativity. It is crucial for the teachers in the engineering field to take student gender, culture, and teaching strategies together into consideration when creating and maintaining a supportive and friendly learning environment for their female students.

Thirdly, gender plays an essential role in engineering creativity and it may have some interaction with other variables [2]. Chang [3] stressed that individual's creativity could be influenced by some variables, such as social environment, motivation, or cultural context. This study suggests that future research could explore the interaction effect on students' engineering creativity by their gender and other personal variables such as academic background or learning experiences.

Finally, this study was conducted with a small sample from three universities in Taiwan. Further research is also needed to determine whether the results obtained here generalize to students in engineering in other Asian societies.

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